

VERB MOOD

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Annotation: *The aim of this course is to provide the readers about the category of mood of the verb. The main aim of the category of mood of the verb is indicates the speaker's attitude to the action expressed by the verb. The mode of the verb determines whether the speaker considers the action real, desirable, doubts its possibility, or considers it conditional or unrealistic.*

Key words: *Mood, Verbs have present, past, and future tenses, Indicative Mood Interrogative Mood, Subjunctive Mood, Imperative Mood, Conditional Mood, Exclamation marks.*

If you study English grammar, you likely know that verbs have present, past, and future tenses that we use to express when something happens. While most English speakers know about tenses, there is a much less commonly known grammatical aspect of verbs: moods. In grammar, a verb mood is used to express a specific attitude. We hope we didn't ruin your good mood by bringing up this rarely discussed part of English grammar. Compared to other languages, the English verb moods aren't talked about much and rarely appear in school lesson plans. In fact, most English speakers use grammatical moods without even knowing they exist. Let's see if we can improve the mood of the oft-ignored English moods by letting them briefly introduce themselves.

What is a mood?

In grammar, a mood is an inflection of a verb used to express a specific attitude or intent of a speaker. Depending on the language, verb moods can be used to express specific ideas, such as probability, doubt, or hesitancy.

According to most sources, the English language has at least three verb moods and may have as many as five. Compared to other languages, English moods are relatively simple, and many English speakers use moods without knowing what they are.

The three main verb moods used in English and many other languages are the *indicative*, *imperative*, and *subjunctive* moods. Some sources also state that English has an interrogative and conditional mood as well, but these two moods are just as often

said to be subtypes of one of the main moods or even types of clauses rather than moods.

Indicative mood

The indicative mood is by far the most commonly used mood in English and the mood you are most familiar with even if you don't realize it. The indicative mood is the mood used to express facts or state opinions as if they were facts. All of the present, past, and future verb tenses can (and usually are) expressed using the indicative mood. The indicative mood is essentially the default mood we use unless we specifically need a different one. This being the case, the vast majority of sentences you say or write will use the indicative mood.

Interrogative mood

The interrogative mood is used to ask questions. In English, interrogative sentences end in question marks and usually contain both an auxiliary verb (helping verb) and a main verb. Often, an interrogative sentence begins with the auxiliary verb and follows with the main verb later in the sentence. Because interrogative sentences are often just rearranged versions of sentences that use the indicative mood, the interrogative mood is often said to be a subtype of the indicative mood or described as a type of sentence or clause rather than a distinct mood.

Imperative mood

The imperative mood is the mood used to issue commands, requests, directions, and similar ideas. A sentence using the imperative mood, known as an imperative sentence, typically follows a specific structure: the base form of a verb is used without a stated subject. The subject of an imperative sentence is an implied you—the you being the person(s) that the speaker/writer is addressing. Imperative sentences often use exclamation marks to express importance, emotion, or urgency.

Subjunctive mood

The subjunctive mood is the most complicated—and least commonly used—of English's three main verb moods. In general, the subjunctive mood is used to express hypothetical situations, wishes, doubts, and demands. The subjunctive mood uses particular verb conjugation rules depending on what the subject and verb of the sentence are. In general, plural subjects use the same verbs as they normally would. However, things get more complicated if you have a first or third person singular subject (like I, he, she, or it) or use the verb be. For example, third person singular subjects drop the -s that would normally be used at the end of a verb.

Conditional mood

The conditional mood is used to express ideas that depend on conditions. The conditional mood typically uses verbs like would, could, and should together with the

word if or when. In English, the conditional mood is not always listed as a separate mood, and when it is, it is often considered to be a subtype of the subjunctive mood.

The Three Moods of Verbs

The three moods of verbs that we commonly use are the imperative, subjunctive and indicative moods. There are other kinds too, such as conditional verbs, which are 'if' statements that highlight if something may or may not happen - but these three form the basis of most sentences, and are useful to focus on while teaching.

In general the number of English moods in different theories varies from two to seventeen. In this work the indicative, imperative and subjunctive moods are considered. The difficulty of distinguishing other moods from the indicative in English is connected with the fact that, barring be, they do not contain a single form which is not used in the indicative mood. At the same time the indicative mood contains many forms not used in other moods. The subjunctive mood is richer in forms than the imperative mood. So the meaning of the three moods are distinguished in the language structure not so much by the opposition of individual forms (as is the case in the opposeemes of other categories), as by the opposition of the systems of forms each mood possesses. By way of illustration let us compare the synthetic forms of the lexeme have in the three moods.

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